

Optimizing Company Profile as a Public Communication Tool in Educational Institutions

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the public communication strategy implemented by Bimbel CEC, a non-formal educational institution, through the use of its company profile. The company profile functions not merely as an informational medium but as a strategic communication tool to build institutional image, convey vision and mission, and reach wider audiences, including prospective franchise partners. This research adopts a descriptive qualitative approach, with data collected through in-depth interviews with two key informants: the Chief Executive Officer and the Co-Founder. Data analysis was conducted using NVivo software with thematic coding to identify key themes. The findings reveal that Bimbel CEC employs a multi-channel communication strategy, utilizing digital, print, electronic, and face-to-face media in an integrated manner. Message formulation emphasizes structured content, audience-based customization, visual storytelling, and soft selling approaches. Strategic adjustments are made regularly in response to technological advancements, curriculum changes, and social media trends. This study concludes that the company profile is not only a promotional asset but also a dynamic communication medium that embodies the institution's values and positioning aligned with Kotler's concepts of integrated marketing communication and strategic branding.

KEYWORDS: Company Profile, Communication, Public Relations, Strategic Branding

INTRODUCTION

A company profile is an institutional communication medium used to introduce the identity, vision, mission, programs, values and advantages of an institution to the public in a systematic and attractive manner. (Sarjono et al., 2023). In the context of educational institutions, company profiles not only function as a promotional tool, but also as a communication bridge between institutions and the public. The preparation of an effective company profile can create a positive perception of the institution and increase public trust, especially when packaged with a strong narrative and visual approach (Lozano et al., 2020). This media plays an important role in building the reputation and legitimacy of institutions amidst increasingly tight educational competition in the era of technological disruption (Sidharta et al., 2024). A company profile that is prepared by paying attention to audience segmentation will be better able to convey the values and goals of the institution in a targeted manner (Putri & Lestari, 2023) Therefore, the design, content and media for distributing the company profile must be adjusted to the characteristics of the target audience, both in terms of age level, social background and information consumption habits (Suyitno, 2021; Sumendap, 2022).

A company profile is a multipurpose strategic document used by organizations to introduce their identity, competitive advantages, organizational structure, and future plans to various parties. A company profile also serves as a communication tool that can be tailored to a variety of audiences, such as potential partners, investors, and the general public (Bhasin, 2020). Key elements that must be displayed in a company profile include a brief history, operational data, number of branches, employees, revenue, as well as the organization's vision, mission, main services, and road map. Meanwhile, according to Michaelidou (2023), a company profile is an official representative of an entity, be it a business, institution, or organization that creates a deep "first impression" to the public and potential clients. A company profile is prepared in a professional and concise format, containing elements of brand identity, main services or products, organizational values, and visualizations that represent the character and culture of the entity. In addition, Karinov emphasized the importance of aligning the contents of the company profile with the purpose of distribution, whether for investors, clients, or the general public, and choosing the right distribution channel so that the message is conveyed optimally. (Michaelidou, 2023)

Public communication in educational institutions does not only include one-way delivery of information, but also a process of exchanging meaning that actively involves stakeholders (Pont, 2020; Sidharta et al., 2024). Effective public communication in education according to media that is able to reach the wider community while building strong emotional connections (Khasawneh,

2024). Company profile in this context acts as a representation of the institution's values as well as an initial dialogue channel with the public. In a public communication strategy, media such as company profiles must be developed through a cross-divisional approach (Ewim et al., 2024; Ardiansyah & Aliya, 2024). This is important so that the message communicated reflects the unity of the image and consistency of the institution's mission. In the digital era, optimizing a company profile as a public communication tool is also determined by adaptation to technology and audience preferences, both through print media, interactive digital, and hybrid (Mahmud et al., 2024).

According to Kotler & Keller (2016), a company profile is part of marketing communications that conveys the company's values and image in a structured manner to build market trust and strengthen differentiation, functioning as a strategic branding tool that reflects the reputation, character and competitive position of an organization in the eyes of the public. (Kotler, P., & Keller, 2016). In non-formal educational institutions such as tutoring, company profiles act as the main instrument to build credibility and differentiation amidst the many choices of similar institutions. An effective company profile not only displays what is offered, but also explains "why this institution is worth choosing" (Widodo, 2024; Afriani & Timan, 2024). This function is in line with the principle of value proposition in marketing communications, namely displaying added value that differentiates the institution from competitors (Putri & Lestari, 2023). Thus, identifying the function and role of a company profile is not only important in terms of visual or aesthetic aspects, but also as part of a public communication strategy that supports the achievement of the institution's vision and mission as a whole. Therefore, this study tries to dig deeper into how this media is optimized by Bimbel CEC in building relationships and shaping public perception effectively and sustainably.

In the context of educational institutions such as Bimbel CEC, company profiles are not only used as a promotional medium, but also as a strategic communication tool that conveys the vision, mission, superior programs, learning methods, and values of the institution to a wide audience. Optimal use of company profiles allows for two-way communication between institutions and the public, especially parents of students, potential business partners, and local communities. In addition, company profile content that is adjusted to audience segmentation and technological developments is an important element in increasing the effectiveness of communication and the competitiveness of institutions. However, optimizing the use of company profiles as a public communication tool still requires special attention, especially in terms of message preparation, selection of distribution media, and impact evaluation strategies. In practice, company profiles are often only used in one direction and have not fully empowered digital features that enable active public interaction and involvement. Therefore, an in-depth study is needed on how public communication strategies through company profiles can be optimized, including the role of Public Relations (PR) in building an image and reaching target markets effectively. This study was conducted to analyze how Bimbel CEC as a non-formal educational institution implements a public communication strategy through company profile media. This study is important as an effort to understand how the integration between content, media, and internal stakeholders can form a communication strategy that is adaptive, participatory, and oriented towards long-term relationships with the community.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive qualitative research design to explore in depth the public communication strategy implemented through the company profile of Bimbel CEC. A qualitative approach is selected because it enables the researcher to interpret meanings, narratives, and communication practices that are socially constructed and embedded within organizational contexts. As noted by Creswell and Poth (2018), qualitative inquiry is particularly suitable for understanding how individuals and institutions construct reality through language, symbols, and interaction. The primary objective of this research is to identify the function of the company profile as a strategic communication instrument in a non-formal educational setting. Rather than treating the company profile merely as a promotional medium, this study conceptualizes it as a communicative artifact that reflects organizational identity, institutional values, and public engagement strategies. By prioritizing depth over breadth, the research examines how narrative framing, visual composition, and message structure within the company profile contribute to image-building and the expansion of public communication reach. This descriptive qualitative design allows for an interpretive analysis of communication practices, emphasizing how meaning is produced and negotiated between the institution and its audiences. The approach also facilitates contextual understanding of strategic decisions made by organizational actors, particularly in relation to branding, audience

segmentation, and two-way communication. Through this design, the study aims to generate rich empirical insights into how Bimbel CEC positions itself within the competitive landscape of non-formal education.

Unit of Analysis and Data Collection Procedure

The unit of analysis in this study comprises Bimbel CEC's company profile as the central communication artifact, supported by related promotional materials and organizational perspectives. Analytical attention is directed toward narrative content, visual presentation, and message structure embedded within the company profile. In addition, organizational communication practices such as audience targeting, feedback mechanisms, and digital engagement are included to provide a comprehensive understanding of the institution's public communication strategy. Data were collected using three complementary techniques: in-depth interviews, documentation, and observation. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with two key informants, namely the Owner and Co-Founder of Bimbel CEC. These informants were purposively selected due to their strategic roles in designing and implementing the institution's communication initiatives. The interviews sought to capture insights into communication objectives, content development processes, and evaluations of the company profile's effectiveness.

Documentation analysis covered the company profile, social media content, and both digital and printed promotional materials. These documents served as primary empirical sources for examining how messages are framed, visualized, and disseminated to the public. Observations focused on Bimbel CEC's digital communication patterns and public interactions, enabling the researcher to contextualize documentary evidence and interview narratives within actual communicative practices. Data analysis was conducted using NVivo 12 Plus to facilitate systematic thematic coding (Jackson & Bazeley, 2019). Interview transcripts and documentary materials were organized into thematic nodes, including communication strategy, public relations roles, audience segmentation, narrative framing, and two-way communication. The coding results were visualized through word clouds and coding matrices to map relationships among themes and identify dominant patterns. To ensure validity and credibility, this study applied triangulation of sources and methods by comparing interview data, documentation, and observational findings (Miles & Huberman, 2014). This triangulated approach strengthens analytical rigor by minimizing single-source bias and enhancing interpretive depth. Through these procedures, the research offers a nuanced understanding of how the company profile functions as a strategic communication instrument within Bimbel CEC's organizational context.

RESULTS

Company profile is a strategic representation of the identity, values, and direction of the institution. In Bimbel CEC, company profile is not only used as a medium of institutional information, but also becomes the main instrument in public communication strategy. Based on the results of interviews and thematic analysis, there are three main objectives to be achieved through the preparation and distribution of company profile: building the image and reputation of the institution, conveying the vision-mission and superior programs, and attracting the interest of business partners and potential franchisees. In addition, company profile is also used to introduce the existence of the institution to the wider community as a credible, adaptive, and competitive non-formal educational institution. The Co-Founder emphasized that the company profile is an important tool for the public relations team to build emotional closeness and public trust in the institution, especially in new areas reached by the branch. This was emphasized through his statement:

"For public relations, the task is to build the image of Bimbel CEC and also to coordinate with the entire team, the goal is for the entire community to understand that Bimbel CEC is relevant to the educational methods that are currently developing" (Co-Founder)

In addition to building internal and external images, the Owner explained that the company profile is also a strategic communication tool to approach business partners and explain the advantages of the CEC Tutoring system to potential investors or franchisees:

"We use company profiles as a medium to communicate with potential partners or franchisees so that they know the system and advantages of our institution." (Owner)

However, the use of company profiles as a public communication tool cannot be done stagnantly. Changes in the external environment such as technological developments, dynamics of educational curriculum, and shifts in audience behavior force Bimbel CEC to continue to adjust and develop strategies for compiling and presenting content in its company profiles. Based on the results of NVivo thematic coding and visualization of relationships between themes, it was found that there are several important aspects that encourage periodic adjustments to strategies, including: changes in social media trends, audience habits, adaptation to new

curricula, design updates, and development of technology-based communication systems. The latest content and format updates are made so that the company profile remains relevant and is able to reach the target audience effectively. For example, when people start to switch to digital media and visual narratives, the preparation of the company profile also adjusts to the storytelling style and soft selling approach. This was conveyed by the Co-Founder in an interview:

"Content updates must be done, because social media trends are changing rapidly. Sometimes from language style, design, to information placement must be adjusted again." (Co-Founder)

This adjustment not only concerns design and language, but also the substance of the content, such as when the national curriculum changes, the learning methods used by Bimbel CEC are also updated in the company profile.

"We also see that many competitors have used new communication models, so we are re-evaluating the format and content of our company profile, especially in terms of how the narrative is delivered." (Owner)

In other words, the strategy for compiling and using company profiles is dynamic and contextual, following market needs and developments in communication media. This process cannot be separated from internal collaboration between the PR, marketing, teaching, and IT teams, who together carry out periodic evaluations and updates. This shows that Bimbel CEC has made company profiles an active communication tool, not just a formal document. Bimbel CEC's company profile plays a dual role: as a medium for institutional representation and as an adaptive strategy to face the challenges of change. When associated with public communication theory and strategic adaptation models, this practice shows that Bimbel CEC has integrated institutional communication with audience needs simultaneously. The strategic objectives and flexibility in adjusting the content and format of the company profile make this media not only technically functional, but also relationally and emotionally meaningful to the public. Based on the visualization of thematic relationships, there is a close relationship between the Company Profile Objectives and the Communication Strategy Adjustment carried out by Bimbel CEC (Figure 1). These two elements are the main foundations in the institution's public communication strategy, which is carried out dynamically by the two key figures: Owner and Co-Founder.

Figure 1. Motivation as Personal Resolve

Figure 1 shows that the purpose of compiling a company profile cannot be separated from an adaptive communication strategy. A company profile is not only a communication product, but also a reflection of the institution's dynamic vision. Bimbel CEC's ability to adjust strategies based on external changes, media trends, curriculum, technology makes it an institution that is not only communicative, but also progressive.

Bimbel CEC utilizes various media and communication channels to disseminate company profiles as part of a public communication strategy. The selection of these channels is adaptive and aims to reach audiences from various circles, both digitally and conventionally. Based on thematic analysis and visualization of relationships between categories, Bimbel CEC uses various media and communication channels that are multi-platform. The media used include digital media, print media, electronic media, and face-to-face communication. The selection of this media is not uniform, but is adjusted to audience segmentation and communication

objectives. This shows that the communication strategy implemented by Bimbel CEC is integrative and adaptive to public needs. Digital media such as websites, Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and Zoom are the main channels to reach urban communities, the younger generation, and parents who actively use digital devices. Informants stated that this digital platform is used to convey more general information and can be updated at any time.

"We use social media as a communication channel, because it is always updated every day so it can be edited easily and is usually more general and can be developed continuously." (Co-Founder)

Meanwhile, print media such as brochures, flyers, tabloids, and banners are used for more specific and formal purposes, especially in communicating with schools, regional heads, and communities that do not yet fully rely on digital media.

"Print media must be more detailed, because it targets people who need written and more complete information." (Owner)

In addition, electronic media such as television and radio are also utilized as part of an offline approach that expands the scope of public promotion and education. Meanwhile, face-to-face communication is still carried out through direct meetings, both with partners, principals, and local communities, especially in regional branches. The thematic relationship image shows that all of these channels are directly correlated with informants and play an active role in disseminating the company profile widely and in layers. The message-making strategy in the Bimbel CEC company profile is designed systematically by referring to the principles of educational, informative, and persuasive communication. The visualization image shows a direct relationship between message-making and elements such as content structure, message adjustment based on segments, visual storytelling, and a soft selling approach. The content structure in the company profile is arranged in a logical and directed order, starting from the introduction of the institution, vision and mission, to learning methods and student testimonials. The goal is to build a complete understanding of the advantages of Bimbel CEC in one integrated narrative.

"We compile our company profile with a narrative starting from the history of CEC Tutoring to the learning method, and all of it must be coherent so that it is easier for the public to understand." (Owner)

This strategy also emphasizes message adjustment based on audience segmentation, such as for elementary, middle, and high school students, and using local languages in certain areas. This adjustment is considered important to build emotional closeness and social connectedness with the areas where the CEC Bimbel branches are located.

"Because our CEC Tutoring branches are numerous and spread across several regions, it means that we also use many languages... very effective for bonding with the local community." (Co-Founder)

Furthermore, the use of storytelling and visual narrative approaches is a key feature in digital company profiles. Instead of just presenting data, content is packaged in the form of inspiring stories, learning activities, and emotionally engaging testimonials.

"We emphasize soft selling. And not hard advertising, or an approach that makes people feel close." (Co-Founder)

In understanding the public communication strategy implemented by Bimbel CEC through the company profile media, it is important to see the relationship between the main elements that underlie the institution's communication practices. It is not only limited to the type of media used, but also includes how messages are structured, adjusted, and delivered to diverse audiences. Therefore, to clarify the structure of the relationship between communication channels and message formulation strategies, the following is a thematic visualization that describes the role of each actor (Owner and Co-Founder), the type of media used, and the message formulation approach applied. This visualization also provides a comprehensive picture of the integrated communication system run by Bimbel CEC (Figure 2). Based on Figure 2 of the thematic visualization, Bimbel CEC's public communication strategy, especially through the preparation and distribution of company profiles, involves two key figures: the Owner and the Co-Founder. Both play a central role in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of messages and communication channels used by the institution. Figure 2 connects two main dimensions: communication channels and message formulation strategies, both of which are pillars in the public communication process.

In the media and communication channel dimension, Bimbel CEC utilizes five main types of channels: digital media such as websites, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Zoom, print media in the form of brochures, banners, flyers, electronic media in the form of TV and radio, face-to-face communication carried out through direct presentations and meetings with schools, and combined communication channels that bridge all of these platforms. The figure shows that both informants, both the Owner and the Co-Founder, are actively involved in using all of these types of media. The selection of channels is based on audience characteristics and communication objectives, allowing for a flexible and effective approach.

Figure 2. CEC Bimbel Company Profile Strategy

Meanwhile, in the dimension of message development strategy, there are five key elements developed by the internal communication team: content structure, message customization based on segments, emphasis on soft selling, storytelling and visual narrative strategies, and strategic and gradual message development. Figure 2 shows that the Co-Founder is directly connected to all of these message development elements, indicating his dominant role in shaping Bimbel CEC's communication style. Meanwhile, the Owner is more strongly connected to the visual narrative element and responsive content, indicating his involvement in monitoring the quality and direction of the message. The relationship between nodes shows that Bimbel CEC's communication strategy is integrative and adaptive. Messages are not only structured with a clear structure, but also adjusted to the audience segment (elementary, middle, high school, or parents), and packaged in a communicative and emotional form through visual storytelling techniques.

All communication channels, both digital, print, and direct, are used synergistically to convey a consistent message. By combining the right media selection and a targeted content strategy, Bimbel CEC makes the company profile a communication tool that is not only informative, but also builds long-term relationships with the community. The findings of this study reveal how CEC Tutoring strategically utilizes its company profile as both a representational medium and a communication tool. To provide a clearer understanding, the results are organized into three key aspects: the objectives of the company profile and its strategic adjustments, the media and communication channels employed, and the strategies used in message composition.

Table 1. Research Findings

Aspect	Main Findings	Details / Explanation
Objectives of Company Profile and Adjustment of CEC Tutoring Communication Strategy	The company profile functions as a strategic representation of the institution's identity, values, and direction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main objectives: (1) building institutional image and reputation, (2) conveying vision, mission, and flagship programs, (3) attracting business partners and potential franchisees. - It also introduces CEC Tutoring as a credible, adaptive, and competitive non-formal educational institution. - Requires dynamic adjustments to respond to technological developments, curriculum changes, and audience behavior.
Media and Communication Channels in Compiling CEC	Multi-channel communication strategy that is integrative and adaptive.	Digital media: Website, Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, Zoom → wide reach,

Tutoring Messages	Company Profile		fast updates, targeting urban communities and younger audiences. Print media: Brochures, flyers, banners → more detailed and formal communication, aimed at schools and communities with limited digital access. Electronic media: TV and radio → expanding offline promotional coverage. Face-to-face communication: Direct meetings with schools, partners, and local communities. Media selection is adjusted based on audience segmentation.
Message Strategy	Composition	Messages are systematically structured, educational, persuasive, and supported by visual storytelling.	Narrative structure: institution's history → vision and mission → learning methods → student testimonials. Content tailored to different segments (elementary, junior high, senior high students, and parents). Use of local languages at branch levels to build social bonding and emotional closeness. Preference for soft selling rather than hard advertising. Visual storytelling (photos, videos, inspiring stories) used to enhance audience engagement.

Overall, the results highlight that CEC Tutoring's company profile is not a static promotional document but rather a dynamic communication instrument. By aligning objectives, media channels, and message strategies, the institution successfully integrates branding efforts with adaptive communication practices, thereby strengthening its image, building trust, and enhancing engagement with diverse audiences.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the company profile at Bimbel CEC acts as a strategic communication media that is used in a planned manner to build the institution's image, expand public reach, and establish relationships with various stakeholders, including students, parents, and potential business partners. This practice is very relevant to the concept of Integrated Marketing Communications proposed by Kotler & Keller (2016), namely the coordination of all forms of messages and communication channels in order to convey consistent, relevant, and integrated information to the target audience. Bimbel CEC uses various communication channels such as digital media, print media and electronic media, to face-to-face communication synergistically. The messages in the company profile are arranged with a visual narrative approach, segment adjustment, and soft selling style, which shows the implementation of a focused but flexible communication strategy following the development of audience behavior. The role of the company profile in introducing the identity, values, and learning methods of Bimbel CEC is also in line with the concept of strategic branding according to Kotler & Keller (2016), namely the process of creating strong perceptions and differentiation in the minds of the public. Company profile is used as a tool to form a positive image that differentiates Bimbel CEC from competitors, while strengthening public trust in the educational services offered. Bimbel CEC's brand positioning as an intelligent, affordable, and adaptive institution is clearly reflected in the structure and style of communication displayed. Thus, the

public communication strategy through the company profile at Bimbel CEC proves that the principles of Kotler's theory can be implemented effectively in the context of non-formal educational institutions. The success of this communication is not only measured by the delivery of information, but also by the institution's ability to build emotional relationships and long-term trust with the public, which is the core of modern strategic marketing.

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